

MICROSTRUCTURES AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF LIQUID-PRESSED A356/SiC_p COMPOSITES

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Keywords: metal matrix composite, A356, SiC particulate, porosity, coefficient of thermal expansion, thermal conductivity

1 Introduction

Aluminum matrix composites with high volume fraction of SiC particulates are used for thermal management applications and optical systems due to their excellent thermal and mechanical properties such as high thermal conductivity, low tailorable CTE, high modulus and low density [1].

Al/SiC_p composites with higher volume fraction of SiC_p have been fabricated mainly by powder metallurgy, pressureless infiltration and squeeze casting method. Among them squeeze casting technology is believed to be an effective technique due to higher production rates and lower production cost. However, higher pressure is needed to assist infiltration for squeeze casting method due to poor wettability between SiC and molten metal. Recently, new fabrication methods - liquid pressing method - have developed to make MMC with higher volume fraction of reinforcement using much lower pressure [2, 3]. When fabricating the Al/SiC_p composites by the liquid pressing method, the soundness of the composite materials differs with the processing variables such as temperature of melt, pressing time and the pre-treatment of the SiC particulates. Accordingly, the thermal properties of the composite materials differ with the processing variables. In the present investigation, the microstructures A356/SiC_p fabricated by liquid pressing method were analyzed and their thermal properties were evaluated.

2 Experimental

The commercial grade of A356 alloy and commercially available 10 μ m SiC particles were used as a matrix alloy and reinforcements, respectively. The plate of A356 alloy and the preform of SiC_p (45vol.%) were inserted into a steel mold. The steel mold was 100mm in diameter and

10mm in thickness. The mold was heated to above the melting temperature of A356 alloy and then pressed (figure 1). During fabrication various processing parameters such as heating temperature, holding time and pre-treatment of SiC particles were changed to improve the infiltration of A356 melt into the SiC particles preform.

The fabricated composites were section and polished for optical and scanning electron microscopy. The porosity of the composites was calculated from the measured density of the composites. The CTE was measured using a DIL402C dilatometer system and thermal conductivity was measured by the laser flash method with the NETZSCH LFA 457.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of liquid pressing method.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Microstructures

Figure 2 shows the macroscopic view of the composite samples with different processing variables. In some processing parameter the A356 melt was fully infiltrated into the SiC_p preform

while inappropriate processing parameter the A356 melt was not fully infiltrated into the SiCp perform to remain void in the center of the sample. The soundness of sample improved with increasing the melt temperature and holding time; these factors improved the fluidity of melt and thus improved the infiltration. In addition, pre-treatment of SiCp by thermal oxidation at 900°C improved infiltration kinetics by the formation of SiO₂ on the surface of SiCp [4].

Fig.2. Macroscopic view of the composite samples.

Figure 3 shows the representative microstructures of the composite sample with pore level less than 0.3%. It can be seen that the composite has a rather uniform distribution of the SiC particles in the matrix and no evidences of pores or separated interface (figure 4), indicating that high volume fraction Al/SiCp composites can be fabricated by liquid pressing method.

Fig.3. SEM micrograph of Al/45vol%SiCp (pore level less than 0.3%).

Fig.4. TEM micrograph of sample shown in figure 3.

However, inappropriate processing parameter the melt cannot fill the space fully, and accordingly some pores were remained in the microstructures (Figure 5).

Fig.5. SEM micrograph of Al/45vol%SiCp (pore level more than 3.8%).

3.2 Thermal properties

The variation of CTE with the pore level was plotted in figure 6 along with the predicted model such as ROM and Turner's model. The measured values of CTE were in the range of 8 to 10 ppm/K, irrespective of the porosity, and the values were

between ROM and Turner's model. It is reported that the thermal expansion of composites is relatively insensitive to voids in the microstructures with a continuous metallic phase [5].

Fig.6. Variation of CTE with the pore level.

The variation of thermal conductivity (TC) with the pore level was plotted in figure 7 along with the predicted model (modified H-J model). Unlike the change of CTE with the porosity, thermal conductivity was affected greatly by the degree of pore in the composites; TC of the sound composites containing less than 0.3% porosity exhibited 155 W/mK while TC decreased greatly with the increase of porosity.

There are several models to predict the TC of the composites. Hasselman and Johnson [6] have shown that the TC of composites with continuous matrix and dilute volume fractions of spherical reinforcements is expressed as

$$K_c = K_m \frac{[2K_m + K_r^{eff} + 2 \cdot (K_r^{eff} - K_m) \cdot V_r]}{2K_m + K_r^{eff} - (K_r^{eff} - K_m) \cdot V_r} \quad (1)$$

with

$$K_r^{eff} = K_r / (1 + \frac{K_r}{ah_c}) \quad (2)$$

where K is the TC, V the volume fraction of particle, and the subscripts c, m and r refer to the composites, matrix and reinforcements, respectively; a is the

radius of the spherical reinforcements and h_c is the thermal boundary conductance.

Recently, modified H-J model is suggested by Molina et al for two-step H-J model [7] and Chu et al for multiple effective medium approximation (MEMA) [8]. Their basic idea is that the pores in composites can be treated as a non-thermally conducting inclusion in the metal and thus the composites is composed of reinforcements and "effective matrix" containing pores. Hence, the TC of matrix (K_m) in equation (1) is replaced by effective TC of matrix as follows

$$K_m^{eff} = \frac{K_m [2 - 2 \cdot V_p]}{2 + V_p} \quad (3)$$

where V_p is volume fraction of pores.

Fig.7. Variation of thermal conductivity with the pore level.

In this work, the TC is calculated using equation (1) with equation (3), putting $K_m = 167\text{W/mK}$, $a = 5\mu\text{m}$, $V_r = 0.45$, $h_c = 7.10 \times 10^7 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and $K_r = 254$ and 400W/mK , respectively. Among the values, thermal conductance, h_c , can be estimated by a simple Debye model to be $6.65 \times 10^7 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ [8]. However, the measured value for Al/SiC composites is about $7.10 \times 10^7 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ [7-9], thus we chose the value in this work. Similarly, it is not easy to obtain the intrinsic value of TC for polycrystalline SiC. The

value of TC for high purity single crystal SiC is about 400W/mK [9], and this value was chosen as an upper limit. In recent investigations [7-9], the value of TC for SiC was deduced from the linear fitting to be 215 to 254W/mK, and thus 250W/mK was chosen as a lower limit.

Figure 7 shows the comparison between the predictions and experimental data for the effect of porosity on A356/SiCp fabricated by liquid pressing method. It can be seen that the increase of porosity causes a pronounced decrease in TC of composites. In the lower porosity less than 3.0%, the experimental data are in good agreement (or even higher values) with the predicted model for upper limit. However, in the high porosity, the experimental data exhibited much lower value compared to the predicted model.

Fig.8. Fractography of samples with (a) pore level more than 3.0% and (b) pore level less than 0.3%.

There are several possible reasons to explain the discrepancy between predicted model and experimental data such as particle shape, volume fraction of particles and presence of pore. Basically, the two modified H-J model (two step H-J model and MEMA) is derived from the H-J model (equation 1). The composites in the present work is a little far from the criteria of the H-J model; the shape of particle is not spherical and the volume fraction is quite high. However, in the lower pore level, the experimental data are in good agreement with the prediction, indicating that the above factors are not so critical to explain the discrepancy between predicted model and experimental data.

The other important reason is the presence of pore. In the modified H-J model (two-step H-J model and multiple effective medium approximation), it is assumed that the pore is present in the matrix, and the effective K_m is calculated using TC of pore is zero by H-J model. However, in the present composites, most of pore is present in the vicinity of SiC particles. Figure 8 shows the fractography of composites samples in the present work. It can be seen that in the composites containing pore less than 0.3%, the SiC particles are surrounded by ductile matrix. On the contrary, in the composites containing pore more than 3.0%, void was formed in the vicinity of SiC particles. It means that the particles and voids are separately embedded in the matrix, instead of particles being embedded in the pore containing matrix for composites with high porosity. It can be expected that the thermal scatter of separated interface will be much considerable compared to that of pore in the matrix. Accordingly, the experimental data obtained in the higher pore level exhibited much lower value compared to the prediction. Thus, the interface bonding between reinforcements and matrix is one of the dominant factors to improve the TC of the composites.

4 Summary

A356/45vol.%SiCp composites have been manufactured successfully by the liquid pressing method. The microstructural analysis reveals that the composite has a rather uniform distribution of the SiC particles and no evidences of pores or separated interface in the matrix. The sound composites containing pore less than 0.3% exhibited low

coefficient of thermal expansion (8ppm/K) and high thermal conductivity (155W/mK), and the experimental data are in good agreement with the predictions.

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